

Project Update 2026

Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing project

Use of the Outdoors & Greenspace research in the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme

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Research Focus: Policy makers, practitioners, and scholars are increasingly recognising the need to foster conditions that support a reciprocal relationship between people and the environment – one that nurtures human communities while encouraging active care for the natural environment.

Aim: To investigate possibilities and constraints for building capacities for such a relationship through aspects of environmental settings (type, quality), users (barriers, behaviours), mechanisms for benefit (green prescribing, outdoor learning), and investment (costs, preventative spend).

New Project Output

Research Strand 1: Investing in Quality Green & Blue Spaces

The benefits gained from green and blue spaces depend on the quality of those spaces. We worked with stakeholders to create a validated green and blue space quality index, and are now finalising a toolkit for improving investment in quality green and blue spaces, including extensions for use with pre and young teen girls.

Journal Article: Nicholson, H., Roberts, M., Thompson, C., Li, K-H., Irvine, K.N. (2025). Examining indicators of quality green and blue space: A mixed method study investigating multifunctionality. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 170, 104100. doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104100

Description: Based on our in-depth reports, this paper details the use of green and blue space quality indicators, and how they can explore multifunctional quality, utilising Scotland as a case study.

Report: Nicholson, H., Roberts, M., Thompson, C., Irvine, K.N. (2024). *Validated index of green and blue space quality*. Report for Scottish Government. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887988

Description: Building on the 68 quality indicators identified in the literature review we carried out a survey and workshops to identify any missing indicators, and to understand the importance and use of these indicators within a Scottish context. [Related literature review report link: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107161]

How is this research funded?

The Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing project is funded by the Scottish Government under the Rural & Environment Science & Analytical Services Division (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027). The programme of interdisciplinary research is carried out primarily by the Government's Main Research Providers (MRPs). The James Hutton Institute is one of these MRPs. One of the topic areas focuses on use of the outdoors and greenspace. This project builds on research undertaken in previous programmes (2011-2016; 2016-2022).

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Research Strand 2: GO: Girls Outdoors

Building on a literature synthesis of linkages between outdoor learning by pre-school and primary age pupils (3-12 year olds) with subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children and young adults, we are undertaking a multi-year study of girls' outdoor engagement across time (childhood, pre-teen, teen). [Review link: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10201267]

Report: Schulz, L., Banks, E., Williams, A., Irvine, K.N. (2025). *Girls Outdoors: key moments for (dis)engagement with nature*. Report for Scottish Government. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17558369

Description: Findings from Wave 1 of the Girls Outdoors Study are reported. Participants (age 10-12) provided insight on patterns of and changes in outdoor engagement since childhood; barriers to and enablers for this behaviour; and outdoor experiences that influenced their (dis)engagement. From these we draw implications for policy, practice, and research. [Methods Technical Report for Girls Outdoor Study link: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17557322]

Research Strand 3: Nature Engagement Capabilities

Drawing on literature, existing data, the Scottish Outdoor Access Code, and novel field-based approaches, we develop and apply frameworks for understanding the opportunities and constraints for engagement with and care for nature.

Research Brief: Irvine, K.N., Brown, K., Thompson, C. (2024). *Nature Engagement and Care: Concepts for Cultivating Inclusive Outdoor Participation and Responsible Outdoor Access*. Report for Scottish Government. The James Hutton Institute, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17558735

Description: This research brief overviews two concepts being developed to inform strategies to foster both inclusive and sustainable engagement with the outdoors. The concepts draw on existing data and debates within the literature.

Research Brief: Conniff, A., Somervail, P., Irvine, K.N. (2024). *Assessing functionality and usability of a virtual tour for nature engagement: brief report*. Report for Scottish Government. The James Hutton Institute, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12621264

Description: Summarises key insight from a study examining the functionality and usability of a virtual tour of an outdoor forest path in Scotland to support nature engagement amongst individuals with limited familiarity of the place. [In-depth report link: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12621881]

Virtual Nature Tours: Virtual Tour of the Oak Path at Cashel Forest in Loch Lomond and Trossachs National Park, Scotland <https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/cashelforestoakpath/>

Virtual Tour of Seaton Park and Donmouth in Aberdeen, Scotland <https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/SeatonDonmouth-Portal/>

Research Strand 4: Science-policy-practice-society interface

Use of the outdoors has multiple benefits. We examine policy and practice interventions that seek to foster behavioural change to enable broad, inclusive, and sustained uptake in nature engagement for impact across society.

Report: Flanigan, S., Premarathne, M., Schulz, L., Somervail, P., Conniff, A., Warber, S.L., Irvine, K.N. (2025). *Critical assessment of the potential of forest therapy as an intervention for health and wellbeing in Scotland*. Report for Scottish Government. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17558778

Description: This report examines the potential of forest therapy as a programme suitable for green social prescribing, its component parts (programme, activity, group, nature), and how it is implemented in practice. The assessment responds to policy interest in the nexus across green space, wellbeing, and leverage points for nature engagement.

Journal Article: Irvine, K.N., Fisher, D., Currie, M., Colley, K., Warber, S.L. (2024). A Nature-Based Intervention for Promoting Physical Activity in Older Adults: A Qualitative Study Using the COM-B Model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(7), 843. doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21070843

Journal Article: Smith, E.S., Marselle, M., Colley, K., Irvine, K.N. (2025). Policy as an approach to behaviour change: encouraging visits to the outdoors during leisure and recreation to promote health and wellbeing in Scotland. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 1–26. doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2025.2540087

Description: These articles utilise the theoretically grounded Behaviour Change Wheel (Michie et al., 2011) to examine government policy and nature-based health promoting programmes as interventions to support increased time outdoors in nature.